

EARTH SCIENCES

DIRECT-PROSPECTING TECHNOLOGY OF SATELLITE IMAGES AND PHOTOS IMAGES FREQUENCY-RESONANCE PROCESSING: RESULTS OF LARGE BLOCKS AND HYDROGEN DEGASSING AREAS SURVEYING IN GREECE AND ITALY

Yakymchuk M.,

doctor of physics and mathematics, professor

Institute of Applied Problems of Ecology, Geophysics and Geochemistry, Kyiv, Ukraine

Korchagin I.

doctor of physics and mathematics, professor

Institute of Geophysics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Abstract

The results of a survey in the reconnaissance mode of large prospecting blocks and hydrogen degassing areas in Greece and Italy are presented. Experimental studies were carried out with the aim of additional approbation of direct-prospecting methods and improvement the methodology of their application in exploration process for oil, gas and natural hydrogen, as well as the of deep structure of Earth structural elements studying. The investigations have been conducted with using the mobile and low-cost technology, that include modified methods of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photo images, vertical electric-resonance sounding of a cross-section, as well as a method of integrated assessment of the prospects of oil and gas potential of large prospecting blocks and license areas. The conducted reconnaissance survey shows that the probability of large oil and gas deposits discovering within Ioannina block is low. In the area around Ikaria Island, it is advisable to conduct detailed prospecting in order to detect and localize hydrogen accumulations in the upper part of the cross-section, above basalts. The results of an integrated assessment of the prospects of the oil and gas accumulations detecting within two search blocks near Crete Island allow more reasonably plan a sequence of further detailed geophysical works within their limits. On the Italy territory the presence of natural hydrogen and living (healing) water accumulations in areas of visible hydrogen degassing was confirmed by reconnaissance studies with direct-prospecting methods using. The conducted survey of a relatively large block in the hydrogen production area in Mali testified of presence in this region of basalt volcanoes with hydrogen and living water. The proven mobile technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing allows filling the studied cross-section with specific rocks (sedimentary, metamorphic and magmatic), as well as identifying areas on the surface and intervals in the cross-section that are promising for ore and combustible minerals prospecting.

Keywords: Greece, Italia, Ikaria and Crete Islands, Ioannina block, limestones, marls, dolomites, basalts, granites, hydrogen, direct searches, deep structure, oil, gas, carbon dioxide, sounding of the cross-section, remote sensing data processing.

Introduction

In 2019-2021 in various regions of the globe, a significant number of experimental research has been carried out in order to test frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photographs processing and decoding [17, 18], as well as to develop and improve methodology of their practical application in solving geological exploration problems of various nature. The results of previous experiments with the aim of testing and practical application of modified frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photographs processing, as well as the developed on their basis methodology of operational integral assessment of the prospects for oil and gas (ore, water) of large prospecting blocks and local areas are presented in published articles and conferences materials, including those in [17-45].

In the course of the work, the possibility of targeted use of mobile direct-prospecting technology was additionally studied for detecting and localizing hydrogen accumulations in areas of visible hydrogen degassing and assessing (determining) the depths (intervals) of their occurrence, as well as an integral assessment of

the prospects for detecting hydrogen deposits within local areas and large prospecting blocks. At present, the problem of searching for natural hydrogen accumulations and organizing its production is quite relevant due to the intention of the world community to switch in the near future to carbon-free energy, in which an important place is given to hydrogen, the environmentally friendly fuel of the future.

We also focus on the fact that in recent years, during the work in almost all areas of the survey, an additional set of measuring procedures has been carried out aimed at detecting volcanic complexes, filled with sedimentary and magmatic rocks of various types, as well as determining the depths of their roots. The results obtained can be used in the future in the development of the main provisions of the "volcanic" model of the formation of structural elements and the appearance of the planet Earth, as well as deposits of ore and combustible minerals, as well as water.

This article presents the materials obtained in the process of conducting experimental studies of a reconnaissance nature within large prospecting blocks in Greece, in a prospecting area in Albania and in three

local areas in Italy. The article also describes the features of the reconnaissance survey projects of the territories of individual countries in order to identify promising areas and sites for detailed prospecting for oil and gas, natural hydrogen, ore minerals and water.

Research methods

Experimental studies of a reconnaissance and detailed nature are purposefully carried out using mobile methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing and decoding, vertical scanning (sounding) of cross-section in order to determine (estimate) the depths and thicknesses of various rock complexes and sought minerals, as well as methods an integral assessment of the prospects for oil and gas potential (ore content, water content) of local areas and large blocks [9, 17-46]. Some methods of the technology used are based on the principles of the "substance" paradigm of geophysical research [9], the essence of which is to search for a specific (searchable in each individual case) substance - oil, gas, gas condensate, gold, iron, water, etc. The developed methods are based on the standing electric waves discovered by Nikola Tesla in 1899 in the deep horizons of the Earth [15-16]. Mobile technology as a whole, as well as its individual methods, are actively used in the testing mode to

search for hydrocarbon accumulations at the initial stages of the geological exploration process, including for the integral assessment of the oil and gas potential of large and hard-to-reach blocks and areas, as well as local areas of prospecting and exploratory wells drilling.

In modified versions of the methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing, as well as vertical sounding (scanning) of cross-section, bases (sets, collections) of chemical elements, minerals, rocks and minerals (specific samples) are used [17]. Thus, the collection of oil samples used in instrumental measurements includes 117 samples, gas condensate - 15 samples.

The set of photographs of sedimentary rocks consists of 11 groups: 1) psephites, monomineralic conglomerates (22 samples, sample numbers in the set are 2-23); 2) psammites (18, 25-42); 3) silts, mudstones, clays (6, 44-49); 4) kaolinite mudstones (6, 51-57); 5) kaolinite clays (10, 59-68); 6) sedimentary-volcaniclastic rocks; tuff breccias (9, 70-78); 7) limestones (24, 80-103) (Fig. 1b); 8) dolomites (11, 105-115) (Fig. 1c); 9) marls (10, 117-126) (Fig. 1d); 10) siliceous rocks (13, 128-140), salt.

Fig. 1. Photographs of rock samples whose resonant frequencies are used during images processing [8]: a) 6th group igneous rocks (gabbros and basalts); b) 7th group sedimentary rocks (limestones); c) 8th group sedimentary (dolomites); d) 9th group sedimentary rocks (marls).

The database of photographs of igneous and metamorphic rocks includes 18 groups: 1) granites and rhyolites (29 samples, sample numbers in the database are 1-29); 2) granodiorites and dacites (7, 31-37); 3) syenites and trachytes (18, 39-56); 4) diorites and andesites (14, 58-71); 5) lamprophyres (14, 73-86); 6) gabbro and

basalts (32, 88-119) (Fig. 1a); 7) non-feldspar ultramafic rocks (20, 121-140); 8) feldspathoid syenites and phonolites (23, 142-164); 9) feldspathoid gabbroids and basaltoids (6, 166-171); 10) feldspar-free ultramafic and mafic rocks (10, 173-182); 11) kimberlites and lamproites (20, 184-203); 12) non-silicate carbonates (8, 205-212); 13) metamorphic granulites (10,

214-223); 14) metamorphic gneisses (26, 225-250); 15) metamorphic crystalline schists (44, 252-295); 16) metamorphic microcrystalline schists (phyllites) (11, 297-307); 17) metamorphosed slates, cleaved sandstone (1, 308); 18) metamorphosed slates, cleaved siltstone (1, 309).

Figure 1 shows only 4 groups of rocks from the sets listed above. When carrying out measurements in different regions, responses at hydrogen frequencies have been obtained at the moment only from these groups of rocks. At the same time, signals of hydrogen were recorded from basalts almost always.

Photos of the used sets of samples of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks are borrowed from the electronic document [4]. Let us add to this that in our publications the rock classification proposed by the authors of the document [4] is also used.

Materials of earlier experimental studies, obtained with the used set of mobile direct-prospecting methods, are presented in publications [17-46]. The same articles describe the methodological features of measurements during the satellite images and photographs processing using the developed technical means.

When conducting numerous studies using the described direct-prospecting methods in 2019-2021, the optimal procedure (processing graph, sequence of actions) was worked out (and constantly improved), which is used when carrying out work within the blocks and areas of survey. The used processing graph for a separate satellite image (or its local fragment) includes the following sequence of actions (steps).

1. Fixation from the surface of the presence (absence) of responses (signals) from the following set of minerals: oil, condensate, gas, amber, oil shale, argillic breccia, gas hydrates, ice, coal, anthracite, hydrogen, living water (deep), dead water, diamonds, brown coal, iron ore, potassium-magnesium salt, sodium chloride salt (hereinafter simply salt).

2. Registration of responses from the groups of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks that make up the cross-section.

3. Establishing the presence of deep channels (volcanoes) filled with various groups of rocks in the survey area; determination of the depths of the roots of volcanoes location.

5. Determination of groups of rocks (or individual samples of groups), from which signals are recorded at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas and water (deep).

6. Establishing the presence (absence) of responses from oil, condensate and gas at the surface (depth) of 57 km - the boundary of hydrocarbon synthesis in deep channels (volcanoes), filled with certain groups of rocks.

7. Establishing the presence (absence) of responses from water (deep) on surfaces (depths) 59 km, 68 km, 69 km - the predicted boundaries of water synthesis in volcanoes of a certain type.

8. By scanning a cross-section with different steps from the surface up to 15 km, depth intervals are determined, within which responses are recorded at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, and gas. Refinement of the depths of location of the most promising for

hydrocarbons intervals of cross-section during additional scanning with a finer step.

9. In case of detection of responses from the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts) on the surveyed area, an assessment is made of the depth of the upper boundary (edge) of basalts, as well as the depths of the beginning of recording responses at resonant frequencies of hydrogen and living (healing) water from basalts.

10. When establishing the presence of signals from the 11th group of igneous rocks (kimberlites) in the survey area, the depth of the upper edge of the kimberlites is determined, as well as the depth interval within which responses are recorded at diamond frequencies.

Given the reconnaissance nature of the studies performed, the described set of separate procedures for satellite images processing in full was not implemented in all surveyed areas.

Once again, we focus on the distinctive feature of the direct-prospecting frequency-resonance methods being developed. Unlike classical geophysical methods, the methods used make it possible in each specific case to fill the cross-section under study with the complexes of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks present in it, as well as to determine in the first approximation (and refine at the stages of detailing) the intervals of cross-section that are promising for the detection of combustible and ore minerals, immediately, in the process of measurements (registration of signals) by the developed instrumentation and measuring devices (i.e. without additional stages of modeling and geological interpretation of the results of instrumental measurements). In this article, as well as in other published materials, the emphasis is mainly on the presentation of measurement results.

In addition to what was said in the previous paragraph, it is worth adding the following. As a result of testing and practical application of the developed measuring equipment in various regions of the world, numerous evidences (facts) have been obtained in favor of the "volcanic" model of the formation of many structural elements of the Earth (and other planets and satellites of the solar system), as well as deposits of combustible and ore minerals (hydrogen and water as well). Instrumental measurements established the existence of 10 types of volcanic complexes filled with various types of rocks. And what is characteristic, the roots of all volcanoes are almost always fixed by scanning the cross-section at the same depths, namely: 95-98 km, 214-218 km, 470 km, 723 km, 996 km.

It is quite natural that the depths of the roots of 470 km or 723 km of a salt or dolomite volcano cause rejection and skepticism among many experts. We also note that at the initial stages of testing the technology, such depths of roots were also surprising to the authors of the experiments. However, the ubiquitous repetition of such depth values during many hundreds of measurement experiments gives grounds for the assumption that such strictly predetermined values of the depths of the roots of various volcanic complexes are due to certain wave processes in the solar system and our galaxy.

In this regard, it is only regrettable that such skepticism in relation to the depths of the roots of volcanoes

is automatically (without detailed consideration and analysis of materials) transferred to the results of instrumental measurements in the upper part of cross-section accessible for drilling.

Reconnaissance survey within Ioannina license block

The Ioannina search block is located in northwestern Greece. Brief information about this large block with an area of 4187 km² is given on the website of the Energean Greek company [5]. Experimental studies on the block territory were carried out with the aim of additional approbation of the methodology for the integral assessment of the prospects for oil and gas potential of large license blocks and local areas, based on the results of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing and interpretation.

Below, in this section of the paper only the results of instrumental measurements using the developed instrumental systems are given. The measurements were carried out on April 25, 2022 within the Ioannina block and on April 28, 2022 on a fragment of Block 4 in Albania, adjacent to the Ioannina block from the north.

We will try to formulate brief conclusions on the results of the instrumental measurements in this part of the paper.

In the reconnaissance mode, the oil and gas prospects of the Ioannina prospecting block on the Greek onshore were assessed using the technology of frequency-resonance processing of the block satellite image (Fig. 1a). During instrumental measurements, integral estimates of some parameters of the cross-section and predicted accumulations of oil and gas were obtained.

Results of instrumental measurements on April 25, 2022. During frequency-resonance processing of the block satellite image of the (Fig. 1a), signals (with a delay) were recorded from the surface at the frequencies of oil (at 24 s), condensate (at 17 s), gas (at 14 s), methane-oxidizing bacteria (at 8 s), yellow phosphorus (at 17 s), sedimentary rocks of 7th (limestone), 8th (dolomite), 9th (marl) - (at 21 s) groups and 14th (gneiss) group of metamorphic rocks.

Fig. 1. Satellite images of the Ioannina Block area.

Within the survey block, the presence of volcanic complexes, filled with dolomites and marls with roots at depths of 470 km and 723 km, respectively, was established. Responses at frequencies of dolomites are recorded in the range of 4.920-470 km, and of marls – 5.080-723 km.

Signals at limestone frequencies were recorded within the block from the interval of 2150-4920 m. This indicates that the central part of the limestone volcano (root) is located outside the block.

Responses from the 14th group of metamorphic rocks (gneiss) were recorded from the interval 0-2150 m.

Fig. 2. Satellite image of the Ioannina Block territory and adjacent areas.

On the surface of 4900 m from the upper part of cross-section, signals were recorded with a delay at the frequencies of oil (at 14 s), condensate (at 11 s), gas (at 14 s), and yellow phosphorus (at 14 s). From the lower part of cross-section at this depth, no responses at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas, and yellow phosphorus were recorded for 60 s.

By scanning the cross-section from the surface, step 10 cm, responses at oil frequencies were recorded from the following intervals: 1) 2304-2341 m, 2) 2579-2588 m, 3) 2632-2637 m.

When scanning the cross-section with a step of 1 m, signals at gas frequencies were obtained from the interval of 2304-2453 m.

During frequency-resonance processing of a larger area with a block (Fig. 2), the presence of a volcanic complex, filled with sedimentary rocks of the 7th (limestone) group, was established within it. Responses

at limestone frequencies were recorded at a depth of 50 km.

On the HC synthesis surface of 57 km, signals were recorded at the frequencies of oil.

The results of image processing in Fig. 2 confirm the conclusion that the central part of the limestone volcano (root) is located outside the Ioannina block contour.

Further instrumental measurements were not carried out at the study block.

Results of instrumental measurements on April 28, 2022. There is information on the site [5] that in the adjacent Block 4 in Albania (Fig. 3), hydrocarbon deposits were found in carbonate rocks. In this regard, frequency-resonance processing of the satellite image of the Block 4 fragment (Fig. 4) was carried out in the reconnaissance mode.

Fig. 3. License blocks of Albania [1].

Fig. 4. Satellite image of a fragment of the Block 4 territory in Albania.

When processing the satellite image in Fig. 4, signals from the 7th group of sedimentary rocks (limestones) and the 14th group of metamorphic rocks (gneisses) were recorded from the surface. The root of the limestone volcano was determined at a depth of 470 km, and responses from granites (old) were obtained from the interval of 470-996 km.

On Fig. 5 photographs of samples of the 7th group of sedimentary rocks (limestones) and oil are presented, the resonance frequencies of which were used during instrumental measurements. When scanning the cross-section from the surface, step 1 m, the responses at the frequencies of this set of samples were recorded from the intervals of 1337-1710 m and 3102-5173 m.

Signals at the frequencies of this set of samples were also recorded at depths of 5, 10, 15 and 57 km! This allows us to conclude that in the limestone volcano

(the 7th group of sedimentary rocks) at the boundary of 57 km, there are conditions for the hydrocarbon's synthesis. Within this volcano, there are also deep channels of hydrocarbon migration to the upper horizons of cross-section.

Main results and comments. The results of experimental reconnaissance work, carried out promptly within the Ioannina block can be summarized as follows.

1. At the very beginning of this part of the paper, we note once again that a limited set of instrumental measurements was made within the Ioannina search block. Above, in fragments of the paper with the results of measurements, integral estimates of the values of the of the cross-section parameters of a fairly large survey area are presented. Point estimates of the cross-section parameters can be obtained during areal studies.

Fig. 5. Photographs of samples of 7th group of sedimentary rocks (limestones) and oil, the resonant frequencies of which are used during instrumental measurements.

2. As during the direct-prospecting methods testing within large blocks and local areas in various regions of the globe, within the Ioannina block additional evidence was obtained in favor of the volcanic model of the structural elements and the external appearance of the Earth formation, as well as deep (abiogenic) synthesis of oil, condensate and gas. Thus, within the surveyed block, the presence of volcanic complexes filled with dolomites and marls with roots at depths of 470 km and 723 km, respectively, was established. Responses at the frequencies of dolomites were recorded in the range of 4.920-470 km, and for marls - in the range of 5.080-723 km.

3. Unfortunately, reconnaissance studies within the Ioannina block did not reveal volcanic complexes, in the contours of which there are conditions for hydrocarbon synthesis at the boundary of 57 km.

4. In many volcanic structures, filled with limestone, conditions for the synthesis of oil, condensate and gas exist at the boundary of 57 km. Responses at limestone frequencies were also recorded within the Ioannina block. However, instrumental measurements have shown that the limestone volcano is located near

the Ioannina block, and the limestone rocks from this volcano overlapped some parts of the Ioannina block. Additional confirmation of these conclusions are the following results of instrumental measurements:

a) fixation at a depth of 50 km of responses at limestone frequencies and signals at oil frequencies at a hydrocarbon synthesis depth of 57 km during frequency-resonance processing of a larger image (Fig. 2) of the territory with the Ioannina block;

b) establishing the presence of a volcanic complex, filled with limestones, within the exploration Block 4, located near the Ioannina block on the Albania territory.

5. According to the results of the reconnaissance survey of the Ioannina block, the probability of discovering large oil and gas deposits within it is low. This preliminary estimate can be confirmed or refuted when additional studies of a detailed nature will be carried out within its limits using direct-prospecting methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing. We also note that the low probability of large oil and gas deposits discovering in the area of

the Ioannina block is confirmed, in principle, by the results of previous studies and drilling of exploratory wells, a summary of which is presented on the website [5].

6. Additional studies of a detailed nature within the Ioannina block can be carried out in order to promptly solve the following tasks:

A) Localization on the block territory of local area, within which responses are recorded at the frequencies of oil, condensate and gas.

B) Carrying out detailed scanning of cross-section on local areas of the oil, condensate and gas frequencies fixing in order to determine the depths and thicknesses of predicted deposits.

C) Determination of rock samples in the reservoirs of oil and gas bearing formations of the cross-section, as well as in the seals that overlap them in the local area of the planned drilling of a prospecting well.

D) Determining the type of oil (light, dark) in oil-bearing formations at the well drilling site.

E) Identification of the types of volcanic complexes, located near the Ioannina block.

7. At the local drilling site of a prospecting well, an additional set of instrumental measurements of a detailed nature can be implemented in the process of preparing for drilling.

8. The results of approbation and practical application of direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing allow us to reasonably conclude that their targeted use

Fig. 6. Satellite image of the territory of Greece.

Frequency-resonance processing of all 209 fragments of the Greece satellite image can be performed quite quickly. During image processing, the following set of measurement procedures is planned to be performed:

a) fixation from the surface of anomalous responses at the frequencies of oil, condensate and gas;

b) registration of signals from the surface at the frequencies of methane-oxidizing bacteria (bacteria whose populations are analyzed in the method of microbiological exploration for oil and gas by MicroPro GmbH from Germany);

c) establishing the presence of a volcanic structure within the survey area, in which there are conditions for the hydrocarbon's synthesis at a depth of 57 km; additional fixation of responses from oil, condensate and gas at this depth;

d) fixing signals at the frequencies of oil, condensate and gas from the lower part of cross-section at

in the search and exploration of oil and gas deposits can significantly speed up and optimize the exploration process. The promptly conducted reconnaissance survey of the territory of Ioannina large block should be considered as additional confirmation of the potential capabilities of mobile direct-prospecting technology. On the other hand, the survey results of the Ioannina licensed block testified to the potential possibility of a reconnaissance survey of the entire territory of Greece in order to identify the most promising areas (blocks) for detailed oil and gas prospecting. Taking into account the voiced opportunities, a pilot project of a reconnaissance survey of the Greece territory has been prepared, in which 209 fragments of a satellite image of this region territory are proposed for frequency-resonance processing.

Project of Greece territory reconnaissance survey for oil and gas prospect areas detecting

For the practical implementation of the project of a reconnaissance survey of the entire territory of Greece in order to identify the most promising areas (blocks) for detailed oil and gas prospecting, the satellite image of the territory of Greece must be divided into separate blocks, the frequency-resonance processing of which will be carried out separately.

One of the possible options for dividing a satellite image of the Greece territory into separate fragments is shown in Fig. 6 and 7. These images with rectangular contours show 209 local fragments for processing.

Fig. 7. Satellite image of southern Greece and the island of Crete.

depths of 5 km, 10 km, 15 km in order to assess the prospects of oil and gas discovering in the deep horizons of cross-section.

The listed procedures of instrumental measurements have fully demonstrated their effectiveness and informativeness in the process of direct-prospecting methods approbation in the areas (sites) of drilling exploratory wells on land and shelf in various regions of the globe.

Additional procedures for instrumental measurements and the features of their implementation within the framework of this project can be formulated (clarified) if the expediency of its implementation will be recognized in Greece.

Within the most promising for oil and gas blocks, found in Greece, detailed prospecting can also be quickly carried out using the methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing.

The prepared fragments of a satellite image of Greece territory (Fig. 6 and 7) can be additionally processed in the reconnaissance mode within the framework of separate projects for identifying blocks, that are promising for detailed prospecting for:

- a) natural hydrogen;
- b) ore minerals of various types;
- c) water.

Within the territories shown in Fig. 6 and 7, the islands of Ikaria (Fig. 6) and Crete (Fig. 7) are also located. In the reconnaissance mode, frequency-resonance processing of the satellite images of the Ikaria Island. and two search blocks in the region of Crete Island was also carried out.

Ikaria Island (Aegean Sea, Greece)

Ikaria Island is an island of centenarians. Previous studies in the regions, where longevity areas are located (including on Ikaria Island), showed that all of them are located above basalt volcanoes in which water is synthesized at a depth of 69 km. Volcanic basalts also contain hydrogen. And hydrogen-enriched water has healing properties and promotes longevity.

This paper presents the results of using direct-prospecting methods to study the deep structure in the area of Ikaria Island in the Aegean Sea, as well as determine the depths of aquifers and possible accumulations of hydrogen. Experimental studies were conducted to

demonstrate the operability and effectiveness of mobile and low-cost direct-prospecting technology.

The document on site [7] provides a summary of the long-livers of the island of Ikaria. The theses of the report [45] provide brief information about the conducted experimental studies of the areas of longevity.

The photograph and satellite image of the island are shown in Fig. 8.

When processing a satellite image of the island (Fig. 8b) from the surface, responses (signals) were recorded only from hydrogen, water, the 8th group of sedimentary rocks (marls) and the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts).

By fixing the responses from basalts at various depths (50, 150, 450, 550, 750, 723 km), the root of the basalt volcano was determined at a depth of 723 km, and the upper edge of the basalts was found in the depth range of 3-4 km.

Responses from marls were obtained from the cross-section interval over basalts.

By scanning a cross-section from the surface, a step of 50 cm, responses at hydrogen frequencies were obtained from the intervals: 1) 89-880 m; from 2600 m go to step 1 m, 2) 2812- (10 cm step) -3182 m; at a step of 1 m, 3) 3507- at a step of 10 m ... (responses traced up to 15 km).

Fig. 8. Photograph (a) and satellite image (b) of Ikaria Island (Aegean Sea, Greece).

Responses from the 14th group of igneous rocks (gneiss), in which there are samples with marl properties, were also obtained from the surface. By scanning the cross-section with a step of 50 cm, the signals from these rocks are recorded in the interval 160-260 m.

By scanning a cross-section from the surface, a step of 10 cm, responses from water were recorded at the following intervals: 1) 40-93 m; 2) 110-400 m (traced only to 400 m).

On the surfaces of 68 and 69 km, responses from water were recorded, and on the surface of 69.050 km, signals were already absent.

A scanning step of 50 cm is quite large. When scanning with this step, only the search intervals are determined, not individual layers. In this regard, in the interval of response fixing at hydrogen frequencies of 89-880 m, an additional scanning with a smaller step was carried out.

When scanning a cross-section from 70 m, a step of 10 cm, responses at hydrogen frequencies from the

8th group of sedimentary rocks (dolomites) were recorded in the following intervals: 1) 89-218 m; 2) 244-356 m; 3) 418-580 m; 4) 650-664 m; 5) 765-812 m; 6) 836-848 m; 7) 871-880 m; 8) 887-893 m.

From the interval 89-893 m, responses were received only from one sample of the 8th group of sedimentary rocks — dolomite oncolytic. Signals of salt and sedimentary rocks of 1-3th groups were also recorded in this interval.

From interval of 356-418 m, there were no responses from water and salt; only signals of 1-3th groups of sedimentary rocks were recorded.

In the depth range 0-89 m, weak responses of dolomites were obtained.

Notes. 1. We emphasize that by scanning a section with steps of 50 cm, 1 m and larger, only response intervals are determined at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas and hydrogen, within which it is advisable to look for productive reservoirs.

2. The depths of the upper and lower edges of individual layers (including productive reservoirs) are determined by scanning the cross-section with increments of 1 cm and smaller.

3. The obtained values of the parameters of the cross-section are integral estimates of the parameters values - not of point character. To obtain the parameter values at the point, it is necessary to process small satellite images or photo-images of the drilling site in area.

Some comments. On the island of Ikaria, reconnaissance studies were conducted.

By scanning the cross-section on the examined block, hydrogen responses were obtained not from basalts, but from dolomites. Previously, non-basalt responses from hydrogen were recorded only on one hydrogen field in the world in Mali [38]. This field is producing hydrogen.

The results of the reconnaissance work allow us to conclude that it is advisable to conduct detailed prospecting in the area around the island in order to detect

Fig. 9. Offshore blocks near the Crete Island.

and localize hydrogen accumulations in the upper part of the cross-section, above basalts.

When conducting detailed work for hydrogen, the search for collectors with healing water enriched with hydrogen can also be carried out.

The results of applying the frequency-resonance technology for processing satellite images and photographs to search for aquifers and accumulations of hydrogen are presented in publications [22, 29, 31-35, 37-43].

Integral assessments of oil and gas potential of two search blocks near Crete Island

Information on the planned geological and geophysical work for oil and gas within the two exploration blocks in the area of Crete is given on site [6].

Completed studies to assess the oil and gas potential of two large blocks in the area of Crete were carried out at the request of the partners of the performers.

Figures 9-10 shows the position of the search blocks in the area of Crete.

Fig. 10. The contours of offshore blocks at Google map of area.

Satellite images of individual blocks, prepared for frequency-resonance processing, are shown in Fig. 11 and 12.

The results of the operatively conducted frequency-resonance processing of satellite images of blocks in Fig. 11 and 12 are as follows. The following

does not indicate specifically within which block the results of frequency-resonance processing are obtained.

Block A. In the case of frequency-resonance processing of the block A image, no responses (signals) were recorded at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, gas, and amber!

Fig. 11. Google map of West offshore block.

Fig. 12. Google map of South-East offshore block.

Within this block, responses from 9th (marls), 10th (siliceous rocks) (good signal) and 11th (salt) groups of sedimentary rocks are recorded. Signals from the used groups of igneous rocks are not recorded.

By fixing responses at different depths within the block A, the presence of deep channels for the migration of fluids, minerals and chemical elements, filled with salt (11th) and siliceous rocks (10th), was established. The roots of these channels are located at a depth of 470 km.

The lower boundary of the 9th group of sedimentary rocks (marl) is located in the depth interval of 6-7 km.

Block B. At the day surface within block B, responses (signals) were recorded at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, gas and amber!

In the cross-section of the block B, the presence of 7th (limestone) groups of sedimentary rocks was established; the responses from all groups of igneous rocks were not recorded.

By fixing the responses at different depths within the block B, the presence of a deep channel filled with limestone was established. The root of the channel is determined at a depth of 470 km.

When scanning the cross-section with a step of 1 m from 0 m and with a step of 5 m from 6 km, the anomalous responses (signals) at the resonant frequencies of oil were obtained from 7 intervals of the cross-section. The upper boundary of the first interval was determined at a depth of 1700 m, and the lower boundary of the seventh interval was determined at a depth of 8980 m. The cross-section was scanned only up to 10 km.

The cross-section scanning was not performed to determine the response intervals at the resonant frequencies of the condensate and gas.

Brief conclusions. 1. The above materials are the results of an integrated assessment of the prospects of the oil, gas and gas condensate accumulations detecting within two search blocks. And nevertheless, even they allow more reasonably to plan a sequence of further detailed geophysical works within their limits.

2. It is advisable to start exploration work within block B. The start of the geological and geophysical survey of block A is recommended to be postponed to a later period.

3. Within block B, performers can conduct the detailed studies using the frequency-resonance methods of satellite images processing. Detailed studies allow you to:

a) detect and localize within the block local anomalous zones of the responses (signals) fixation at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, gas;

b) within the limits of the mapped anomalous zones with using the technique of cross-section vertical scanning, determine (and refine using a smaller scanning step) the depths of the response intervals at the resonant frequencies of oil, gas and condensate;

c) within the response intervals at the HC frequencies, determine the types of reservoir rocks;

d) establish what types of rocks are tires for the detected response intervals at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate and gas;

e) determine the types of oil and condensate from which the signals (responses) within intervals of the cross-section are recorded (in frequency-resonance methods 117 samples of oil and 15 samples of gas condensate are traditionally used).

4. In general, the results of detailed frequency-resonance processing of satellite images of Block B will significantly speed up and optimize the process of developing the oil and gas resources of this block.

Areas of hydrogen degassing in Italy

In Italy, a limited number of instrumental measurements was made within three local areas of hydrogen degassing, the position of which is indicated on the satellite image (Fig. 13) by rectangular contours.

Area 1 (Fig. 13, rectangle 1). Signals from basalts, hydrogen and living water were recorded at the site. The lower boundary of the basalts is determined at a depth of 99 km. From the 99-470 km interval, responses were obtained from the 9th group of sedimentary rocks (marls).

Fig. 13. Satellite images of local areas of hydrogen degassing in Italy.

Area 2 (Fig. 13, rectangle 2). Signals from basalts, hydrogen and living water were recorded within the site. The lower boundary of the basalts is determined at a depth of 99 km. From the interval 99-218 km, responses were obtained from the 8th group of sedimentary rocks (dolomites), and from the interval 218-723 km - from the 10th group of sedimentary rocks (siliceous rocks).

Area 3 (Fig. 13, rectangle 3). Signals from basalts, hydrogen and living water were recorded in the contours of the site. The lower boundary of the basalts is determined at a depth of 99 km. From the interval 99-218 km, responses were obtained from the 9th group of sedimentary rocks (marls), and from the interval 218-723 km - from the 10th group of sedimentary rocks (siliceous rocks).

During frequency-resonance processing of the entire image in Fig. 13 signals from basalts, hydrogen and living (healing) water were also recorded.

Detailed instrumental measurements were not carried out at the survey sites.

The territory of Italy surveyed in the reconnaissance mode (Fig. 13) is promising for the detection of deposits of natural hydrogen and living (healing) water.

It should be noted that a project of reconnaissance survey of the entire territory of Italy has also been prepared in order to identify areas and blocks that are promising for detailed prospecting for oil and gas, natural hydrogen, ore minerals and water. This project is similar to the project of Greece territory reconnaissance survey for oil and gas prospect areas detecting, described above.

One of the possible options for dividing a satellite image of the Italy territory into separate fragments is shown in Fig. 14 and 15. These images with rectangular contours show 89 local fragments for processing.

Fig. 14. Satellite image of the territory of Italy.

Fig. 15. Satellite image of southern Italy.

We emphasize once again that instrumental measurements of a detailed nature were not carried out at the survey sites in Italy. The main purpose of reconnaissance studies is to confirm by direct-prospecting methods the presence of accumulations of natural hydrogen and living (healing) water in areas of visible hydrogen degassing, as well as in areas where basalt rocks are spread. Detailed studies with the aim of searching for accumulations of hydrogen and living (healing) water in Italy (within local areas in Fig. 13 including) can be carried out jointly with specialists from Italy (if such studies are of interest, of course).

Hydrogen production area in Mali

Currently, the extraction and use of natural hydrogen for the energy supply of a small village is carried out only in Mali. The results of a reconnaissance survey of a production site using direct-prospecting methods are presented in [38]. There are regret that no additional prospecting work has been carried out in this region. In

this regard, in Mali, in the area of hydrogen production, a reconnaissance survey of a larger area was carried out. Satellite images of the work area are shown in Fig. 16.

When processing the image in Fig. 16a with a fragment cut in a rectangular contour from the surface, responses of red and yellow phosphorus, hydrogen, living water, salt, sedimentary rocks of the 8th (dolomites), 9th (marls), 10th (siliceous) groups and igneous rocks of 6th (basalts) and 11th (kimberlites) groups are recorded. Signals of graphite and weak signals from diamonds were also recorded.

When scanning the cross-section from the surface, with a step of 1 m, responses from basalts began to be recorded from 780 m, and with a step of 25 cm, from 825 m. And when scanning from 750 m, with a step of 10 cm, the upper edge of the basalts was recorded at a depth of 818 m.

Fig. 16. Satellite images of the area of natural hydrogen production in Mali.

On the surface of 780 m, responses from dolomites and hydrogen were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section. At a depth of 750 m, responses of basalts from the upper part of the cross-section were not received.

When processing an image of a smaller area (Fig. 16b), signals of red and yellow phosphorus, hydrogen (without delays), living water (without delays), dolomites and basalts were recorded from the surface.

When scanning the cross-section from the surface, with a step of 10 cm, responses of basalts began to be recorded from 52 m, and with a step of 1 m, from 85 m.

On the surface of 52 m, responses from dolomites and hydrogen were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section.

The conducted survey in reconnaissance mode of a relatively large area in the region of the hydrogen production site in Mali testified to the presence in this region of basalt volcanoes with hydrogen and living water. Exploration work to discover new deposits of hydrogen in this area is expedient to continue.

It is worth noting that hydrogen production in Mali is carried out by the Canadian company Hydroma Inc. Information about this company, as well as brief data about the hydrogen production site, is available on the website [3]. Company holds an operating license for gaseous hydrogen covering an area of 1264 km². Hydroma Inc. is the first company to successfully produce electricity using natural hydrogen (Fig. 17), without greenhouse gas emissions. The tests have been successfully completed and electricity is already supplying part of the village of Bourakébougou (Fig. 18 and 19).

Fig. 17. Pilot unit for the production of electricity from the natural hydrogen of Bourakébougou [3].

Fig. 18. Village of Bourakébougou – Electricity from natural hydrogen [3].

Fig. 19. Village of Bourakébougou – Electricity from natural hydrogen [3].

The site [3] also provides a satellite image of the licensed area for the production of natural hydrogen by Hydroma Inc. Using this image, a project of reconnaissance survey of the block was prepared. One of the possible options for dividing a satellite image of the license

block into separate fragments is shown in Fig. 20. These images with rectangular contours show 65 local fragments for processing.

Fig. 20. Satellite image of the Mali territory (fragment).

Key findings and conclusion

The results of instrumental measurements, presented above, are additional to the materials published in [17-45], which demonstrate the potential of super-operational direct-prospecting methods during profile and areal geophysical surveys conducting. Satellite images of local areas and large blocks, as well as photographs of surveyed objects are fundamentally important sources of information about the deep structure of the Earth and minerals in its bowels.

The conducted experimental studies should be classified as reconnaissance ones – within the contours of the blocks and areas of the survey, a limited number of measuring procedures was carried out. When processing the satellite image of big blocks, integral estimates of the values of cross-section parameters are obtained. So, by scanning the cross-section with large steps (50 cm and 1 m) only the intervals of searches (localization) of gas-bearing formations are determined.

In the process of experimental work performing using the methods of satellite images and photographs processing, additional facts (evidence) were obtained in

favor of 1) deep (abiogenic) genesis of oil, condensate and gas in the process of hydrogen degassing of the Earth [2, 14], 2) migration of gas (methane), carbon dioxide and hydrogen into the atmosphere of the Earth planet, and 3) a "volcanic" model of the formation of structural elements and the external appearance of the Earth, planets and satellites of the solar system, as well as deposits of hydrocarbons, ore minerals and water.

According to the results of the reconnaissance survey of the Ioannina block, the probability of large oil and gas deposits discovering within it contours is low. It is necessary note that the low probability of large oil and gas deposits discovering in the area of the Ioannina block is confirmed, in principle, by the results of previous studies and drilling of exploratory wells, a summary of which is presented on the website [5].

The results of Ikaria Island reconnaissance surveying allow us to conclude that it is advisable to conduct detailed prospecting in the area around the island in order to detect and localize hydrogen accumulations in the upper part of the cross-section, above basalts. When conducting detailed work for hydrogen, the search for

collectors with healing water, enriched with hydrogen, can also be carried out.

The results of an integrated assessment of the prospects of the oil, gas and gas condensate accumulations detecting within two search blocks near Crete Island allow more reasonably plan a sequence of further detailed geophysical works within their limits. It is advisable to start exploration work within block B. The detailed studies using the frequency-resonance methods of satellite images processing can be conducted also within block B by performers.

On the Italy territory the presence of accumulations of natural hydrogen and living (healing) water in areas of visible hydrogen degassing was confirmed by reconnaissance studies with direct-prospecting methods using. It is reasonable the detailed studies to carry out with the aim of accumulations of hydrogen and living (healing) water searching on Italy territory.

The conducted survey in reconnaissance mode of a relatively large block in the area of the hydrogen production site in Mali testified of the presence in this region of basalt volcanoes with hydrogen and living water. Exploration work to discover new hydrogen deposits of in this area is expedient to continue.

Let us add to the above that experimental studies of the same nature as in Italia, Mali and Icaria Island have been carried out also at local sites of hydrogen degassing in Ukraine, Belarus, Russia, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, France, Great Britain, Greenland, USA, Spain, Portugal, Japan, and also within several longevity regions on Earth.

The results of the reconnaissance work in Mali are included in the article in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of direct-prospecting methods during the survey of the area within which hydrogen production is carried out.

The results of experimental studies carried out at sites of hydrogen production and drilling wells, as well as at areas of visible hydrogen degassing in different regions, allow us to state the following.

1. In the areas of the basalt volcano's location with roots at different depths, signals at hydrogen frequencies from the surface are almost always recorded.

2. Responses from hydrogen are recorded when the cross-section scanning practically from the upper edges of basaltic volcanoes to their roots. This feature makes it possible to suggest that basalt volcanoes are a kind of channels, through which active migration of hydrogen occurs to the upper horizons of cross-section and further into the atmosphere.

3. In some types of basalt volcanoes at a depth of 68 km or 69 km, deep (living) water is synthesized. Hydrogen-rich water is healing and can be used for wellness purposes. It is advisable to note once again that all surveyed zones and sites of longevity on Earth are located within (contours) of basalt volcanoes, in which water synthesized at a depth of 68 km or 69 km migrates to the surface and is used for water supply and drinking.

4. Hydrogen deposits can be formed by basaltic volcanoes in sealed reservoirs, adjacent to basalts. The Mali hydrogen production site is located outside the contour of the basalt volcano; the hydrogen responses

were recorded from the marl at wells sites. On the island of long-livers Ikaria, as well as on the local survey site in the Carpathians, signals from hydrogen were obtained from dolomites.

5. Hydrogen deposits, formed near basalt volcanoes in different types of reservoirs, can be promptly discovered and localized during areal exploration using methods of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photo-images.

6. The problem of studying reservoirs in crystalline rocks (including basalts) deserves attention. Direct-prospecting technology can also be used for this purpose.

7. Recently, informational messages have appeared about the intentions of some of the world's leading oil companies to start producing "green" hydrogen using renewable energy sources. At present, technologies for producing hydrogen from water have been developed and tested. All that remains is to invest in the construction of technological complexes for its production in the immediate vicinity of the objects of its consumption. And in the case of a delay in the development of effective technologies for prospecting and transporting hydrogen, a situation may arise that the geological industry of the world economy will lose the race for financing projects for the large-scale use of environmentally friendly fuel of the future – hydrogen.

In many publications, including [8, 13], it is noted that the efficiency of prospecting and exploration for oil and gas does not exceed 25–30%. It is also stated here that the main reasons for this situation are “the dogma of the organic genesis of hydrocarbons and the orientation of deep drilling towards positive structural traps of the sedimentary cover, the fund of which is currently close to exhaustion” [13]. At the end of this article, the authors also draw “attention to the need for a mass transition to “direct” prospecting, which is important in the conditions of low success in hydrocarbon exploration” [13].

The authors of the monograph [14] in the introduction write (state) that in «the South Caspian Basin, the largest Western multinational companies and their consortium for period from 1995 to 2008, having drilled 28 exploratory wells with depths up to 7301 m on 21 highly promising structures, previously surveyed by high-resolution 3D seismic, did not discover a single commercially viable field, spending about \$1 billion on their search» [14, p. 10].

The results of a reconnaissance survey of the drilling site of a “dry” well, as well as two prospecting blocks on the shelf of Turkmenistan [46], indicate the expediency of using direct-prospecting technologies in the exploration process. The article [36] presents the results of a survey of areas in the Caspian Sea, where underwater volcanic structures are located.

In Norway, using new technologies, projects are being implemented to analyze materials from drilled wells in order to detect missed oil and gas intervals. Information about these projects is given in documents on sites [10, 11]. These documents note that more than half of the wells drilled (1250) in the North Sea turned out to be dry!

Tested in various regions of the world and used to solve search problems, the direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing can be successfully used to detect missed productive horizons in drilled wells. This is evidenced by survey materials of well drilling sites in various regions.

It is also worth noting that the cross-section scanning method can be used to detect and identify promising oil and gas horizons in the cross-section interval, below the bottom of the drilled wells.

In general, the results of the performed survey of a local area and big blocks in different region indicate the feasibility of using direct-prospecting methods and technologies during studying the deep structure of small areas and large blocks by traditional geophysical methods. The proven mobile direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing makes it possible to "fill" the cross-section under study with specific rocks (sedimentary, metamorphic and magmatic), as well as to identify areas on the surface and intervals in cross-section that are promising for the ore and combustible minerals searching.

The results of reconnaissance studies, conducted in different region of the globe [17-46], also indicate that super-mobile direct-prospecting methods can be used to assess the prospects for oil and gas (ore) potential of large exploration blocks and local areas (including those put up for auction), to select the optimal locations (sites) for laying exploration and production wells, assessment of the prospects for discovering oil and gas deposits in the deep and super-deep horizons of cross-section, prospecting and localization of zones with deep channels location, through which the chemical elements, fluids and mineral matter migrate into the upper horizons of cross section.

References

1. Albania - Oil and Gas. <https://www.privacyshield.gov/article?id=Albania-Oil-and-Gas>
2. Bagdasarova M.V. (2014). Earth degassing is a global process that forms fluidogenic minerals (including oil and gas deposits). *Electronic journal "Deep Oil"*. No. 10. pp.1621-1644. (in Russian).
3. Hydroma Inc. <https://hydroma.ca/en/natural-hydrogen/>
4. "Electronic petrographic reference book-identifier of magmatic, metamorphic and sedimentary rocks" for operational use in the creation of Gosgeol-kart1000/3 and 200/2 for the territory of the Russian Federation. St. Petersburg, 2015. <http://rockref.vsegei.ru/petro/> (in Russian).
5. Energean: <https://www..com/operations/greece/ioannina/>
6. ExxonMobil-Total-ELPE sign agreement for energy exploitation off Crete. <https://www.keeptalkinggreece.com/2019/06/27/greexe-exxonmobil-total-elpe-crete-energy/>
7. Ikarria. <http://www.li.ru/interface/pda/?jid=3286968&pid=434877075&redirected=1&page=0&backurl=/users/3286>

968/post434877075/?fbclid=iwar2e6kto1gxdw2ux9qv uas3clmmgakejqzlbxgcnab78hudz6nnapnf7li

8. Kryvosheyev V.T., Makogon V.V., Ivanova Ye. Z. The main reserve of accelerated effective opening of oil and gas fields in Ukraine. *Mineral resources of Ukraine*. 2019. # 1. P. 31-37. (in Ukrainian).

9. Levashov S.P., Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N. Frequency-resonance principle, mobile geoelectric technology: new paradigm of geophysical investigations. *Geofizicheskiy zhurnal*, 2012, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 166-176 (in Russian).

10. New Technology Unlocks New Insight from Old Wells. <https://www.oceannews.com/news/energy/new-technology-unlocks-new-insight-from-old-wells>

11. NPD sees potential for missed pay in North Sea wells. <https://www.offshore-mag.com/regional-reports/north-sea-europe/article/14206377/norwegian-petroleum-directorate-sees-potential-for-missed-pay-in-north-sea-wells>

12. Rachinsky M.Z., Karpov V.A. On the issue of increasing the efficiency of exploration work. // *Geology and subsoil use*. 2022. No. 1. P. 158-161 (in Russian).

13. Rachinsky M.Z., Kerimov V.I. Geofluid dynamics of oil and gas potential of mobile belts. Scientific editor: M.V. Gorfunkel. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey, and Scrivener Publishing LLC, Salem, Massachusetts. 2015. 494 p. (in Russian).

14. Shestopalov V.M., Lukin A.E., Zgonik V.A., Makarenko A.N., Larin N.V., Boguslavsky A.S. *Essays on Earth's degassing*. Kiev, BADATA-Intek Service. 2018. 632 p. (in Russian).

15. Tesla N. *Patents*. - Samara: Publishing House "Agni", 2009. - 496 p. (in Russian).

16. Tesla N. *Articles*. - Samara: Publishing House "Agni", Moscow: Publishing House "Russian Panorama", 2010. - 584 p. (in Russian).

17. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Bakhmutov V.G., Solovjev V.D. Geophysical investigation in the Ukrainian marine Antarctic expedition of 2018: mobile measuring equipment, innovative direct-prospecting methods, new results. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 1, pp. 5-27. (in Russian).

18. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N. Integral estimation of the deep structure of some volcanoes and cymberlite pipes of the Earth. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 1, pp. 28-38 (in Russian).

19. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Ukrainian Shield: new data on depth structure and prospects of oil, gas condensate, gas and hydrogen accumulations detection. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 2, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

20. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Levashov, S. P. Direct-prospecting mobile technology: the results of approbation during searching for hydrogen and the channels of migration of deep fluids, mineral substances and chemical elements. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 2, pp. 19-42 (in Russian).

21. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Peculiarities of depth structure and of oil and gas perspectives

of Ukrainian shield separate blocks by results of frequency-resonance sounding of cross-section. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

22. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Application of mobile frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photo images processing for hydrogen accumulations searching. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 19-28 (in Russian).

23. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Studying the internal structure of volcanic complexes of different type by results of frequency-resonant processing of satellite and photo images. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 4, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

24. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Technology of frequency-resonance processing of remote sensing data: results of practical approbation during mineral searching in various regions of the globe. Part I. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 29-51; Part II. *Geoinformatika*. 2019. no. 4, pp. 30-58; Part III. *Geoinformatika*. 2020. no. 1, pp. 19-41; Part IV. *Geoinformatika*. 2020. no. 3, pp. 29-62; Part V. *Geoinformatika*. 2021. no. 3-4, pp. 51-88. (in Russian).

25. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Approbation of direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photo images at known hydrocarbon deposits in different regions. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 3-38 (in Russian).

26. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Yanushkevich K.P. Approbation of frequency-resonance methods of satellite and photo images processing on the geological structure "Chicxulub Crater". *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 39-49 (in Russian).

27. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. On the possibility of application the frequency-resonance technology of satellite images and photos images processing for studying objects of the solar system and far space *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 98-108 (in Russian).

28. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Yanushkevich K.P. Features of the depth structure and prospects of oil and gas potential of the Carpathian region by results of cross-section frequency resonance sounding. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 50-68 (in Russian).

29. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonant processing of satellite images and photos images: results of use for determining areas of gas and hydrogen migration to the surface and in the atmosphere. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 3, pp. 3-28 (in Russian).

30. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. New evidence in favor of the abiogenic genesis of hydrocarbons from the results of the testing of direct-prospecting methods in various regions of the world. Reports of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. 2020. № 9. P. 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.15407/dopovid2020.09.055> (in Ukrainian)

31. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photo images: potential opportunities and prospects of application for natural hydrogen accumulations searching. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 4, pp. 3-41 (in Russian)

32. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Depth structure features of large zones of hydrogen degassing in various regions of the earth by results of frequency-resonance processing of satellite and photos images. *Geoinformatika*, 2021, no. 1-2, pp. 3-42 (in Russian).

33. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. On the prospects of the technology of remote sensing data frequency-resonance processing using when conducting profiles geoelectric and seismic studies. *Geoinformatika*. 2021. no. 3-4, pp. 18-50. (in Russian).

34. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Bakhmutov V.G. Features of the deep structure of individual areas within the basalt complexes in Volyn. Problems of regional geology in the west of the East European Platform and adjacent territories: Proceedings of the III Intern. scientific conf., Rep. Belarus, Minsk, 15 Dec. 2021 / Belarus. state un-t; editorial board: O. V. Lukashev (editor-in-chief) [and others]. - Minsk: BSU, 2021. P. 30-36.

35. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Results of a reconnaissance survey of large zones of hydrogen degassing in various regions of the world. Reports of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. 2022. № 1. P. 79-91. <https://doi.org/10.15407/dopovid2022.01.079> (in Ukrainian)

36. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Javadova A. Results of a survey by mobile direct-prospecting methods in the location of the active Dashly volcanic complex in the Caspian Sea. *Azerbaijan Geologist*. # 25, 2022. P. 42-53. <https://www.azgeologist.com/geolog/>

37. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Javadova A. Application of Frequency-Resonance Methods of Satellite Images Processing for Hydrogen and Living Water Accumulations Searching Within Local Areas in Europe. 11 p. 7th World Multidisciplinary Earth Sciences Symposium (WMESS 2021). IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science 906 (2021) 012080. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/906/1/012080

38. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. Application of frequency-resonance methods of satellite images processing for hydrogen and living water accumulations searching within local areas in Mali and Italy. // European scientific discussions. Proceedings of the 6th International scientific and practical conference. Potere della ragione Editore. Rome, Italy. 2021. Pp. 197-206. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/vi-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-european-scientific-discussions-25-27-aprelya-2021-goda-rim-italiya-arhiv/>.

39. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. Application of frequency-resonance methods of satellite images processing for hydrogen and living water accumulations searching on islands of long-livers Okinawa and Icaria // Science and education: problems, prospects and innovations. Proceedings of the 8th International scientific and practical conference. CPN Publishing Group. Kyoto, Japan. 2021. Pp. 177-189. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/viii-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-science-and-education-problems-prospects-and-innovations-28-30-aprelya-2021-goda-kioto-yaponiya-arhiv/>.

40. Yakymchuk M., Korchagin I. Application of frequency-resonance methods of satellite images processing for hydrogen and living water accumulations searching within local areas in Great Britain // The world of science and innovation. Proceedings of the 11th International scientific and practical conference. Cognum Publishing House. London, United Kingdom. 2021. Pp. 202-217. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/xi-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-the-world-of-science-and-innovation-2-4-iyunya-2021-goda-london-velikobritaniya-arhiv/>
41. Yakymchuk M., Korchagin I. On the prospects of natural hydrogen accumulations detecting in Western Europe // Actual trends of modern scientific research. Proceedings of the 11th International scientific and practical conference. MDPC Publishing. Munich, Germany. 2021. Pp. 274-284. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/xi-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-actual-trends-of-modern-scientific-research-6-8-iyunya-2021-goda-myunhen-germaniya-arhiv/>
42. Yakymchuk M., Korchagin I. On the prospects of methane and natural hydrogen deposits discovering in the southeast Texas of USA // Fundamental and applied research in the modern world. Proceedings of the 11th International scientific and practical conference. BoScience Publisher. Boston, USA. 2021. Pp. 198-209. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/xi-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-fundamental-and-applied-research-in-the-modern-world-9-11-iyunya-2021-goda-boston-ssha-arhiv/>
43. Yakymchuk M., Korchagin I. Features of the deep structure within areas of hydrogen degassing in Greenland, Canada and Bermuda triangle // World science: problems, prospects and innovations. Proceedings of the 10th International scientific and practical conference. Perfect Publishing. Toronto, Canada. 2021. Pp. 161-171. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/x-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-world-science-problems-prospects-and-innovations-16-18-iyunya-2021-goda-toronto-kanada-arhiv/>
44. Yakymchuk M., Korchagin I. Results of application the frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photo images processing at sites of search wells drilling. Danish Scientific Journal, No. 35, 2020, Vol. 1. p 27-34. http://www.danish-science.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/DSJ_35_1.pdf
45. Yakymchuk, M., Korchagin I. Application of mobile frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photo images processing for water accumulations searching. 19th EAGE International Conference on Geoinformatics - Theoretical and Applied Aspects. Kyiv, 11-14 May 2020. CD-ROM Abstracts volume. Abstract 17647_ENG. 5 pages. https://eage.in.ua/?page_id=388
46. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Javadova A. Peculiarities of the West Turkmenian offshore part of South Caspian by direct prospecting methods. Reports of European Academic Research. February 2022. Publisher: "EASR". SciPub.de. P. 56-68. <https://ojs.scipub.de/index.php/REAR/issue/view/31/50>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359438120_PECULIARITIES_OF_THE_WEST_TURKMENIAN_OFFSHORE_PART_OF_SOUTH_CASPIAN_BY_DIRECT_PROSPECTING_METHODS#fullTextFileContent